

Personal and Stigma-related Experiences among Clients Treated and Suspected for Lassa Fever in Selected Endemic Communities in Southwestern Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Stigma and discrimination against infected individuals pose significant barriers and can negatively affect access to treatment, care, and support services. Most previous studies on Lassa fever targeted community knowledge and attitude, neglecting the experiences of those who suffered from the disease.

Objective: To assess personal and stigma-related experiences among clients treated for and suspected of Lassa fever in selected endemic communities in Ondo State in southwestern Nigeria.

Methods: This was a descriptive cross-sectional qualitative study involving four focus group discussions with twenty-eight clients who were earlier treated for or suspected of Lassa fever. The discussion guide was managed with simple content analysis.

Results: Respondents suspected of or treated for Lassa fever experienced varying degrees of stigma from their families, the community, and even the health workforce, which made them feel rejected and segregated, and modified their health-seeking behaviour.

Conclusion: Stigma reduction will require coordinated raising of awareness that targets the health workforce and the communities where clients live.

Key words: Lassa fever, stigma, discrimination, clients, Nigeria

Introduction

Unlike most viral haemorrhagic fevers that are recognized only when outbreaks occur, Lassa fever is endemic in parts of West Africa (including Nigeria), with estimated tens of thousands of cases annually.^[1] From 1st January to 10th November 2019, 4,500 suspected cases were reported from 23 states in Nigeria.^[2] Of these, 764 were confirmed positive, 19 probable, and 3,717 negative (not a case). Median age of the suspected cases was 24 years, and the male-to-female ratio for confirmed cases was 1:1.^[3] The observed case fatality rate among patients hospitalized for severe Lassa fever was 15–50%.^[3] About 80% of people who become infected with Lassa virus

have no symptoms, and about 1 in 5 infections result in severe disease in which the virus affects several organs such as the liver, spleen, and kidney.^[4]

Transmission of Lassa virus to humans can occur via inhalation of primary aerosols from infected rodent urine, ingestion of or direct contact with food contaminated with rodent urine, or direct contact of broken skin with rodent excreta.^[4] A study^[5] asserted that poor awareness and knowledge of Lassa fever were found among community members. However, the society contributes to stigmatization and, ultimately, the spread of the disease.

Stigma is the disapproval of or

discrimination against a person, based on perceivable social characteristics that serve to distinguish them from other members of a society.^[6] Individuals who are stigmatized may feel different from and devalued by others. Stigmatization does not only change clients' behaviours, but it also shapes their emotions and beliefs, thereby altering their personality traits. The stigmatized are ostracized, devalued, scorned, shunned, and ignored. They may experience discrimination with respect to employment and housing.^[7] Young people who experience stigma associated with infectious disease may face negative reactions from their peer groups. All these can substantially increase the suffering of infected individuals and can be strong disincentives to promptly seeking medical care.^[7] They can also lead to labelling, discrimination, prejudice, separation, stereotyping, and loss of status by the stigmatized individual.^[8]

Few studies have attempted to address the perceived psychosocial component of Lassa fever in Nigeria. Most research done on Lassa fever in Nigeria examined community knowledge and attitude to the viral infection as well as preventive practices; most have not studied the feelings of the clients themselves. Personal experiences of clients are however important in order to design coping and prevention strategies. This research will help to fine-tune measures by which members of communities affected by Lassa fever can be orientated on the responsibility of accepting and reabsorbing people treated for the disease. The objective of this study was therefore to assess personal and stigma-related experiences among clients treated or suspected for Lassa fever in selected communities of Ondo State where the disease is endemic.

Methods

This was a community-based descriptive, cross-sectional qualitative study among clients who had been completely treated for or suspected of Lassa fever within the past four years in Ondo State, Nigeria. The state has a projected total population of about 4,489,756 based on the 2006 population

census, and it is distributed into eighteen local government areas (LGAs).^[9] It shares borders with Edo State, which is the epicentre of Lassa fever outbreak in Nigeria, and it has the second highest number of Lassa fever cases as well as the only regional specialized centre for the diagnosis and management of Lassa fever in southwestern Nigeria (Federal Medical Centre, Owo).

The minimum sample size for the study was calculated using the modified Leslie Fischer's formula,^[10] and the 26.98 calculated sample size was rounded up to 28. A list of all treated and suspected clients in the four high-volume LGAs in Ondo State was obtained from the State Department of Health. Seven cases were selected per LGA through systematic sampling of one in three names on the list.

The instrument for this study was a pretested focus group discussion (FGD) guide revised by the state epidemiologist and a consultant virologist in the state civil service. Four FGD sessions were conducted with seven respondents at each LGA headquarter. The FGDs were conducted in Yoruba and English languages, with the moderator and 2 assistants in charge of audio recording. Recorded responses were subsequently transcribed verbatim. The socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents were collected using a checklist.

Ethical approval and permission to enrol participants in the study were obtained from the Research Ethics Committee of Ondo State Ministry of Health, while written informed consent was obtained from every client who participated in the study.

Data were analysed with simple content analysis. Responses were directly reported in some instances, while similar group responses were merged in other instances. Socio-demographic characteristics were presented in a frequency distribution table.

Results

Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

There were four FGD sessions with seven participants each. The mean age of respondents

was 42.9 ± 2.3 years, and half of them were within the age range of 40–49 years. The sex distribution of respondents was 17 (60.7%) males and 11 (39%) females. Their major occupation was trading (13, 46.4%), 17 (60.7%) respondents were married, while 19 (67.9%) had up to primary education, as shown in Table 1.

Respondents' understanding of the causes of Lassa fever

All respondents (except two) gave similar views on the causes of Lassa fever, and they opined that contact with rats amidst poor hygiene and improper waste disposal and management is the commonest cause of Lassa fever in our society. A respondent said, “Lassa is caused by inhaling some matter in the air contaminated with infected rat urine or droppings”. Another respondent said, “Direct contact with a sick person's blood or body fluids is the cause of Lassa fever”. Another respondent said that “the disease is mainly spread to humans through contamination with the urine or faeces of infected rats”.

The first of the two respondents who disagreed with others said the association of Lassa fever with rodents is just coincidence, while the second said, “Remember, in this our local environment, we have many bush rodents, which happen to be the sweetest meat, and you tell a person not to eat that meat because it causes Lassa fever. Before this time, long before this time, there has never been a sickness called Lassa fever. You have to involve the community people; let them see the ill effects of eating bush rat meat raw without proper cooking.”

How respondents contracted Lassa fever

The discussants gave their views with similar responses on this subject. An elderly respondent said, “I contracted Lassa fever by consuming food infected by rats”. Another respondent said, “That bad evening, I didn't know that the *garri* (cassava flour) I used to prepare *eba* (cassava flour meal) had been infected by rats. I just found that a week after, I was feeling dizzy and vomiting. So I called my son to take me to the hospital for treatment, because I thought it was malaria, but it was later

diagnosed to be Lassa fever”. Another respondent said that she thought she had been infected with Lassa fever, but she was eventually diagnosed to have malaria. She said, “Thank God it wasn't Lassa fever. I and all my family members have been confirmed Lassa fever-free”. Several respondents did not know how they contacted the disease. One of them said, “Up till as we are talking, I don't really know how I was infected. I just know that I had Lassa fever”.

How respondents knew that they had Lassa fever; by whom and where they were told

Some respondents stated that fever, vomiting, and general weakness are common symptoms of Lassa fever. One woman said, “I discovered that I had malaria symptoms, then I was feeling that my face was swelling”. In another group, a young man said, “I thought it was a fever or diarrhoea, but when I got to the hospital, it was diagnosed to be Lassa fever by the doctor”. One man however insisted that he did not have Lassa fever: “I am sure I don't have Lassa fever. I only have malaria or fever, but the doctor insisted that I should do Lassa fever test to be sure of my ailments”. A man said that “bleeding from the mouth and nose can lead to Lassa fever, because this kind of illness usually puts a lot of people into stress on what may likely be the problem”.

All discussants asserted that they took a lot of steps before reporting to the health facility. Such steps included visiting medicine stores, using herbal medication, seeking for treatment advice from neighbours, and visiting herbalists with the hope that it was just a minor fever or malaria. A respondent aired his opinion thus: “I asked my son to get me medicine from a nearby medicine store in our community, but I was still persisting in the symptoms till I was rushed to the health facility and I was referred to Federal Medical Centre”. In a similar response, an elderly respondent said, “My actions made the infection this bad. I didn't know it was Lassa fever until I got to the hospital, and I was asked to do some tests before they later confirmed that I had Lassa fever”.

How respondents felt within themselves when they were confirmed or suspected of having Lassa fever

Most respondents gave similar views about how they felt when they heard that they (possibly) had Lassa fever. According to a respondent, “I was so depressed when I was suspected as a Lassa fever carrier, though I was later counselled by the doctor on the proper care available for it, if found that one is infected”. Another respondent said, “When I was told that they were yet not sure that my illness was not fever or diarrhoea, I was so destabilized with the fear of it being Lassa fever, until they confirmed it to be malaria after series of tests done”. Another respondent said, “The fear of Lassa fever came upon me from the first day I started feeling dizzy, vomiting, and feeling headache, until my doctor confirmed to me that it was not Lassa fever but another fever, and I was treated and discharged after 3 days”.

Personal experience about Lassa fever

Almost all the respondents said they had fear of death when the symptoms were too much for them to bear. A female respondent said, “Why won't I fear death? I am still too young to experience this kind of pain. My children are still too young to lose their mother. I have to be fearful because if I die now, nobody can take care of my children the way I will take care of them. They are my world”. Common symptoms felt by majority of the respondents include sneezing, headache, and body ache. These symptoms made majority of the respondents to fear death, and one respondent gave this remark: “A situation in which a man has so much plans for the present and the future of his family, but due to a serious pain or illness he is unable to make his plans work—this alone can lead to the fear of dying young. The body pain was so much”. A similar remark was given by another respondent who said, “The value placed on my family is very high. Many of them are too young to live alone now, and I can't give out my underage children for guidance due to death from a sickness. My thought has been on how I'll get better and take care of my family”.

Experiences of stigma from family and the public

Majority of the respondents said that the disposition of even those who were close to them was essentially that of discrimination and neglect. However few respondents said their families were with them for support when they were sick. A respondent said, “My people gave me some distance reservation as a terrible infectious disease like Lassa fever is usually perceived to be dangerous, and some family members actually described it to be as contagious as Ebola, with the potential of easily terminating the life of whoever is infected”. A respondent said, “I felt rejected as family members and others exercised concerns of me infecting them”. Another respondent said, “In my own case, my family members were supportive during this trying period because many of them believe that the disease is treatable, and this would create a chance for my quick recovery from sickness”.

Many of the respondents said they were actually stigmatized, most especially by the public.

“I was isolated in the community and unfairly treated like, for example, someone with witchcraft. Even my sister never came back to check on me, and not even any of her children or her husband did. People class you as a dead person because you have been infected. Many run away from you, and as for your family, they even think you are mad, and that relationship is spoilt; it is broken”. Another respondent said, “There appears to be a clear understanding that Lassa fever can be contracted through contact with an infected person. In fact, fear of contracting the disease through human contact led to my (and my family's) being a victim of isolation and stigmatization, even after recovery. Many of my close pals refused to come and visit me after discharge from the hospital”. A respondent who was suspected to have the disease explained, “If people know you have LF, they also think that you should not talk to or touch people. When my wife was admitted to Lassa ward, well, it was not only an economic depression; it also created social embarrassment because my children no longer went to the neighbours' houses, or to their

relatives... so that is why it is a complete social embarrassment". A respondent also said, "They do tell themselves not to move close to me so that I will not infect them. I remember a day when a friend came to check me at the clinic and one of the nurses asked her to enter and discuss with me. She refused to enter and told the nurse not to worry, that she was okay: she just wanted me to see that she came around". More worrisome was when a respondent said, "Even the health workers do discriminate against suspected patients, for them to prevent being infected. I remember vividly when I was admitted and while awaiting my test result from Irrhua Specialist Hospital, a nurse refused to move close to me, not to talk of paying attention to my care. She was just looking at me from a far distance until the doctor that diagnosed me let her know that it was just a fever".

Community acceptance of the respondents

Respondents also gave their views about their acceptance in their various communities. Many of them said they were rejected by their communities, and it was only few of their family members who were with them. A typical remark read thus: "Our right was tampered with—a lack of political and government commitment to implementation and enforcement of United Nations' Convention on the Right of the Lassa Fever Patient". Another respondent opined, "We were not positively accepted by the community; stigmatization is no doubt an obstacle to achieving good result on community acceptance of people suspected of or treated for Lassa fever".

How respondents have been coping with life after treatment

A respondent exclaimed that "there is a disconnect between community members and Lassa fever-suspected and treated patients due to fear of being infected by an infected person. There is misinformation and poor enlightenment. I think there is apathy to government policies on the treatment and prevention of Lassa fever by the citizens, and probably that is why many communities rejected infected people". Another

stakeholder reiterated that "everybody has roles to play to prevent Lassa fever-infected patients from committing suicide as a result of community rejection, stigma, and discrimination". Few respondents asserted that they have been living a reserved life due to hospital admission and restriction on their movement by health workers. To buttress this point, a man said, "You cannot live a normal life when you have been restricted from doing some certain things".

Discussion

In our study, a significant proportion of our discussants admitted that they experienced stigma and discrimination because they were suspected or confirmed as Lassa fever-infected persons and getting treated for a disease that is deadly and communicable. This supports other similar studies that concluded that stigmatization of clients suffering from disease outbreaks is a common occurrence.^[11,12]

Stigma has been defined as a mark of shame or an attribute that is deeply discrediting within a particular social interaction.^[13] Stigmatization can pose significant barriers and negatively affect access to care and treatment.^[14,15] These can substantially increase the suffering of infected individuals and can be strong demotivators from promptly seeking medical care. Consequent to such delays in treatment is the propensity for affected individuals to remain undetected in the community.

Our study reported anxiety, apprehension, worry, and hopelessness among respondents during the period of treatment, and this could prompt a client not to adhere fully to medications most especially after discharge. In similar supportive studies, stigma and discrimination were reported to be associated with poor medication adherence,^[16] more anxiety, excessive worry, and avoidance of coping strategies.^[17,18] Our study reported condemnation and neglect that prompted respondents to feel depressed. In yet another study, it was found that stigma could lead to suicidal ideation.^[19,20]

While prevention and coping strategies remain germane for the survival of humans,

stigmatized individuals are deprived of them because people feel it may be risky to mingle with carriers or people who have recovered from Lassa fever.^[21] In the study by Ighedosa and colleagues,^[22] both healthcare workers who treated patients with haemorrhagic fever and survivors of the disease were found to be prone to stigmatization, and they demonstrated psychological symptoms.

In support of individual experience of stigma recorded by our study, testing of an attributive model of stigmatization found that people strongly expressed negative feelings about individuals with HIV/AIDS and tuberculosis (TB) in significant numbers, while patients with severe acute respiratory syndrome, a less known threat, encountered less negative attitudes.^[23]

Also in support of family- and community-level stigma and rejection faced by some respondents in our study, in another study, a Kenyan woman with TB told a United Nations investigator in November 2009, “The kind of discrimination I faced from my neighbours made me regret sharing my condition with them; I could not even share the communal sink”.^[24] These expressions are no doubt illustrative of a long history of stigmatization in human communities when contagious diseases strike.^[25-27] Stigma

associated with infectious disease can be a barrier to adopting healthy behaviours, thus leading to more severe health problems and difficulty controlling infectious disease outbreaks of public health importance.

Conclusion

Stigmatization of clients suffering from or suspected of having Lassa fever is a significant finding of this study. This could pose significant barriers to recovery from the disease and negatively affect clients' coping strategies, including willingness to access care, treatment, and support services. Such attitude toward infected persons should be discouraged, and this would require coordinated raising of awareness that targets the health workforce, clients themselves, and most especially, the communities where clients live.

Declarations

Acknowledgement: Authors wish to thank all focus group discussants for giving their time and consent to participating in this qualitative study.

Funding: No external funding was received towards the conduct of this research.

Conflict of interest: There is none within and between listed authors.

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Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents (N=28)

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage
Age (Mean= 42.9 ± 2.3), years		
20–29 years	1	3.5
30–39 years	8	26.6
40–49 years	14	50.0
≥50 years	5	17.9
Sex		
Male	17	60.7
Female	11	39.3
Occupation		
Civil service	4	14.3
Farming	8	28.6
Trading	13	46.4
Others	3	10.7
Marital Status		
Married	17	60.7
Single	9	32.1
Divorced/Separated	2	7.1
Education		
No formal education	5	17.9
Primary	19	67.9
Secondary	3	10.7
Tertiary	1	3.6